

DIARY OF DISPLACEMENT FROM AL-MAWASI- CASE FROM GAZA 2024

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ABSTRACT

The displacement of Gazan families during the 2023/2024 war has led to significant challenges, including the dangers of movement, finding safe shelter, and living in inadequate tents without necessities like water, gas, and food. Displaced individuals struggle with scarce income and a lack of money, often relying on charity-led initiatives for survival. The community has adapted through specialisation and division of labour within the camps, though issues like aid theft and transportation difficulties further complicate their lives. Despite these hardships, resilience remains an essential, albeit forced, response for survival as families face the complexities of life in displacement, including the phenomenon of marriages in tents and the struggle to maintain social connections.

This paper explores the significance of displacement diaries during the war on Gaza, emphasising their role in humanising the conflict, documenting realities on the ground, countering misinformation, and advocating for awareness and solidarity with the Palestinian people. Through a qualitative ethnographic approach, the study examines the daily lives of displaced Gazans, capturing their resilience amid extreme adversity. The case study of Al-Mawasi provides a detailed narrative of the displacement experience, highlighting the physical and emotional challenges individuals and families face.

The findings reveal the critical importance of these detailed diaries in preserving cultural identity, offering psychological relief, and influencing international opinion. The research underscores the need for continued documentation and advocacy to address the humanitarian crisis and support the displaced population of Gaza. This study implies that it provides missing details of the daily life of the displaced Gazans and the amount of suffering and resilience these people are putting to the world to wake up.

Keywords: Gaza, Displacement, Diary from War & Conflict Zone, Resilience, Shelter, Basic Necessities, Aid Theft, Local Charity Initiatives, Community Adaptation.

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1.0. INTRODUCTION

Displacement diaries from Gaza during the 2023/2024 war hold significant importance to the international knowledge community for several reasons. The most important ones are related to humanising the conflict, documenting the reality on the ground, countering misinformation about Gazans and Palestinians, creating advocacy and awareness about the genocide, they bring sources of psychological relief and empowerment to those trying to survive day by day and moment by moment.

2.0. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Importance of Displacement Diaries during the Wars

Displacement diaries provide unique perspectives that often get lost in broader media coverage. These diaries allow individuals to share their stories, emotions, cultural and historical preservation and day-to-day experiences, bringing a human face to the conflict. These narratives help people worldwide connect with the Palestinian issues with those affected, fostering empathy and understanding. These diaries are firsthand accounts of the realities faced by those displaced by the conflict. They document the challenges, fears, and uncertainties of living through war, providing a detailed record that can be valuable for historical documentation, academic research, and policy-making.

In conflict zones, misinformation and propaganda can distort the reality of the situation. Displacement diaries, written by those directly experiencing the conflict, offer an unfiltered view that can counterbalance biased or inaccurate reports. They provide authentic voices that contribute to a more accurate understanding of the situation.

These diaries can be powerful tools for advocacy towards Free Palestine. By sharing their experiences, displaced individuals can raise awareness about their plight, potentially influencing international opinion and prompting humanitarian action. The personal stories can galvanise support for relief efforts and push for diplomatic solutions.

For the individuals writing these diaries, documenting their experiences can be therapeutic. It allows them to process their emotions, assert control over their narrative, and maintain a sense of identity and agency amidst the chaos. Sharing their stories can also foster community and solidarity among displaced persons.

In the face of destruction and displacement, these diaries help preserve the cultural and social fabric of Gaza. They capture the people's resilience, traditions, and daily lives, ensuring that their experiences and cultural identity are not lost to history.

2.2. Early Displacement Trauma

Debre and Jobain (2023) described the trauma of the displacement early during the first month of the war. They described the rotten debris on Gaza's streets, which the displaced Palestinians who are crowded into a squalid tent camp have to live up to. Taking that most people in Gaza are descendants of refugees from the 1948 war, this is not a normal war for them. Even from the first two weeks of the war on Gaza, many Palestinians have lost or fled their homes due to the intense Israeli bombardment, and many started to construct the tent.

2.3. Deteriorating Health of the Displaced

The Palestinian Civil Defence Service in the Gaza Strip announced that cases of respiratory diseases have been spreading as a result of people lighting fires to prepare food due to the scarcity of cooking gas crisis. This situation became more alarming over the last ten months since the war started due to the Israeli occupation, and continued prevention of the entry of cooking gas into Gaza. The primitive means was lighting fires using wood and charcoal, which has caused many to suffer from respiratory diseases, especially those not used to cooking in this way. MEM (2024)

Ahmed (2023), after just a few weeks from the war on Gaza, mentioned that the long queues of people waiting to fill jerry cans are now ubiquitous across the territory as water becomes increasingly scarce, a result of restrictions on water and power imposed by Israel. Even on 3rd November, none of the water pipes from Israel into Gaza were working – although two of the three are now functioning – and a pipe connecting the southern towns of Rafah and Khan Younis is leaking. Ahmed mentioned that the spread of stomach flu with symptoms including abdominal cramps, vomiting and diarrhoea among the kids could be linked to their sleeping on the floor in cold weather and the contaminated water they were drinking daily.

Figure (1) Showing the Children's Role in Sourcing Water for their Families

Courtesy of The Guardian

Ref: Lack of clean drinking water for 95% of people in Gaza threatens health crisis

<https://www.theguardian.com/global-development/2023/nov/04/lack-of-clean-drinking-water-for-95-of-people-in-gaza-threatens-health-crisis>

2.4. How Gaza Resilience Lab Focused on the Issues of the Displaced

Gaza Resilience Lab is an initiative established by the International Inspiration Economy Project (IIEP) and one of its entities, the Socioeconomic Institute for Advanced Studies. (SIAS). The Lab started directly after the War on Gaza in October 2023. Most of the lab publications and studies focused on issues relevant to the displaced population of Gaza.

The Lab covered issues relevant to overcoming resilience fatigue, food scarcity, health and environment, children's learning and wellbeing, besides economic resilience. Finally, the Lab also called for solidarity with the displaced.

2.4.1. Overcoming Resilience Fatigue of the Displaced

The Gaza Resilience Lab focused on the importance of dealing with loss and coping with yearning for lost livelihood to avoid resilience fatigue. The Lab called for capitalising on the 'social capital' to overcome the intentional famine created by the Israeli occupation and also how to manage chaos due to food shortages and limitation of aid. Buheji (2024b), Buheji and Hasan (2024a), Buheji and Hasan (2024b)

The Lab has seen that Gazans have many 'reasons to live' and holdfast to this life, as they have many things to do to continue the resistance journey till 'Free Palestine' becomes a reality. Overcoming feelings of betrayal and letdown to extend resilience is not a choice. Rather, it is a must to attract the world's attention. The other means for overcoming resilience fatigue is to deal with 'collective pain' through 'collective happiness'. Buheji (2024a), Buheji (2024c), Buheji and Mushimiyimana (2024).

Since value-based resilience stories from Gaza are inspiring the world, the Lab mentioned the importance of war survival stories in recent history, which would help maintain the agility of resilience and sustain the hardiness of the Gazans. Al-Muhannadi and Buheji (2024), Buheji (2023), Buheji and Mushimiyimana (2023b)

2.4.2. Food Scarcity, Health and Environment

The other dimension of Lab focus was studies that illustrate the type of acute food insecurity leading to famine among Gazans, especially among the displaced. The Lab also mapped and linked the health risks and how to mitigate the risks of environmental impacts. Hassoun et al. (2024), Buheji and Al-Muhannadi (2023), Shorrab et al. (2024)

2.4.3. Children's Learning and Wellbeing

In regard to children's development, education, learning and wellbeing, the Lab set a mitigation plan to manage the risks of slow children's development during and after the war in Gaza. The scholars of the Lab also mapped the informal learning for displaced learners and how to rehabilitate their wellbeing through storytelling. Buheji and Buheji (2024), Phusavat and Buheji (2024), Buheji and Khunji (2023).

2.4.4. Calling for Solidarity with the Displaced

Finally, the Lab called for solidarity with the Gazans, especially those living in miserable situations of the displaced. The solidarity studies focused on the situation of the collective punishment till ethnic cleansing and genocide, besides it called for empathetic movement with Gazans all over the world. Buheji et al. (2024), Hasan and Buheji (2024)

3.0. METHODOLOGY

This paper involves a qualitative research approach, using ethnographic methods such as participant observation and interviews to gather in-depth insights into residents' lived experiences. The researchers immerse themselves in the community to observe daily routines and conduct unstructured interviews or narrate stories from the field to provide context.

Data is analysed thematically to identify patterns and narratives, with careful attention to ethical considerations like informed consent and confidentiality. This approach captures the complex social dynamics and personal experiences in Gaza, though findings may be subjective and context-specific.

4.0. CASE STUDY – DIARY FROM DISPLACEMENT (AL-MAWASI-GAZA)

4.1. Background of Displacement

After the seventh of October, the war of extermination broke out against the entire 2.4 million population of Gaza. This war also led to the killing, wounding and loss of more than 200,000 Palestinians, which is 10% of the population, which is the highest percentage of killing, wounding and loss in any of the world wars in any country in the world.

For this reason, the fear of Israeli Defence Forces (IDF) killing led to people moving directly from one area to another in the city or neighbouring cities. The IDF got used to destroying buildings directly after it took control of the area, whether it was vacant or destroyed. It even destroys the buildings over the people's heads without any hesitation. This raises the question: where do the displaced people go, where do they stay, how do they move, and what do they carry?

4.2. Displacement and Dangers of Movement

All of Gaza has become threatened, and no place is safe anymore. The occupation declared it a safe area today but will be unsafe tomorrow. Once people are asked to evacuate, they are usually given hours, and the indiscriminate shelling begins on the populated area or the evacuated area.

The first author shares his friend's story during this displacement. It is a general story that can be generalised to all the people in Gaza. There was an eviction threat to the new camp area in Nuseirat, and Muhammad lives there with his wife, 6 daughters, and his elderly mother and father. His father said, "I will not leave or be displaced even if I am killed." They tried with him, but he refused, and after an effort, he agreed to let them leave and leave him at home, so his son Muhammad decided to stay with him to persuade him to leave tomorrow, but the Israeli bombing did not give him time for tomorrow, so he was martyred with his father one hour later. This story is like hundreds and many tragedies that can be heard from the strip since October 7th, 2023. Many of these stories end up erasing the entire families from the Gazan-Palestinian civil registry.

Accordingly, displacement has become necessary according to the assessment of each displaced person for himself and his family. The decision to displace oneself does not mean just a word or just a simple decision. However, it is a critical decision with major financial and moral consequences, as well as effort, fatigue, and risk. From here, more suffering begins. It is difficult to find a transport vehicle for people and to carry some of the necessities for life in the tent, besides the wood and the shade that would be the source for building the displaced shelter. The transport fare, especially if a car, would normally be more than 1,500 Shekel, i.e. about 15 times as much as it was before the war. The displaced family usually carries with them the minimum requirements, only the necessities of life, and they have to leave many of their legacy and memories behind. This emotional feeling of leaving very dear things in a shelter or a house expected to be demolished within hours cannot be further described.

One of my colleagues, a professor at our university, was describing his last displacement scene by saying, 'I went out to the street madly while the shells felled in his house, but we survived me and my family because of the well of God. Luckily, I managed to stop one car in the middle of the road and negotiated with him for 1,500 Shekel. However, I did not own this amount since all the money has been exhausted during these months. After repeating the displacement process 5-10 times. We were displaced from Rafah to Al-Mawasi to find a place to stay, but we could not. Then, we continued driving for about 15 kilometres to find a spot of land in what used to be the Al-Zawaida neighbourhood and on the street.

Here, we decided to set up our new tent. It is a tent that does not protect against heat, cold, wind, or rain, and does not protect any privacy.

4.3. Where to settle and reside after displacement

Many of the displaced families are not used to living in tents. Hence, they live for a month or so, and then they try to find a place with walls. They do that so that they avoid living in the intense heat. Most of the time, they might end up renting a bombed place in which a room remains without walls. If they are lucky, they might have a room with a kitchen, and the rent would be between USD \$400-700. Only very few people in Gaza can afford to pay such rent every month.

Some people search for a place with relatives, neighbours, or strangers who would offer them housing for free for a short period until they could manage their lives and find stability in another place. But most people, meaning about 90%, live in tents because they cannot find or afford a place with walls and because they do not have to pay any rent. These people know that the priority is to use whatever they have money left to buy money, food, water, medicine, and so on.

4.4. The Nature of Living in The Tent

4.4.1. Describing the Tent of the Displaced Family

You can imagine the suffering when a displaced family moves suddenly to a tent that barely brings them together without any of the necessities of civil life, such as no water, electricity, internet, gas and, of course, no toilets. You can now imagine life after that. Here, another life journey starts when all the displaced family members start looking for the queues for water, the coupons for food, gas, transportation, and so on.

The tent or perch that is being prepared while we are in this extreme heat in the summer, you cannot stay in it for a single hour during the day due to the intense heat. The area of the tent is 3 x 3 or 4 x 4, which can barely accommodate a family of 5-6 people. The head of the family tries to make a shelter in front of the tent, perhaps to provide shade in the heat, but to no avail, as the heat is unbearable. After completing the tent setup in the newly displaced area, the family started to search for life's requirements again.

Figure (1) Example of Displaced Gazans Tents

Courtesy of AP News

<https://apnews.com/article/palestinians-refugees-israel-gaza-hamas-civilians-siege-3f55618a0672c839afe961c8aaa2b7ea>

4.4.2. The Water of the Displaced

Most places of displacement do not have water. Municipal water supply lines are completely non-existent, and some projects provide free water tanks in some displacement camps. If you want free water, you must queue for hours to get a gallon (18 litres) or two. The same struggle is repeated if one wants to drink fresh water. In most cases, families would need to find and buy fresh water and regular water for life's needs. One gallon costs from 1-4 shekels, depending on the region and its distance from water sources. You look at the displaced people; and one of them is carrying two jugs of water for a distance of 500 meters or more, and he repeats the attempt several times a day, so you can imagine the amount of suffering the whole family goes through all the day.

Figure (2) Example of Displaced Gazans Water Collection Que

Courtesy of The Guardian

Ref: Lack of clean drinking water for 95% of people in Gaza threatens health crisis

<https://www.theguardian.com/global-development/2023/nov/04/lack-of-clean-drinking-water-for-95-of-people-in-gaza-threatens-health-crisis>

You even need water to cool certain food. For example, when you buy a watermelon, you might not be able to eat it because it is extremely hot. So, some people would use 'the displaced invented tent refrigerator', where they dig a hole in the shade and spray some water to moisten the place and then the watermelon is buried for some hours. If this is not done, the watermelon would not be cooled, and the family can't eat it.

4.4.3. The Gas vs. Cooking on Firewood for the Displaced

Gas for cooking is only available on special occasions, as it is only allowed to enter Gaza in small quantities that do not satisfy the real needs of people, the bakeries, or anything else. When a gas truck enters Gaza, there are lengthy procedures and registrations to purchase half a can of gas, meaning only 6-8 kilograms, and many people are unable to purchase this quantity, as it requires long waiting hours. Those who have to buy gas can buy it on the black market at a price of about 30 dollars per kilogram. Thus, most people started to depend on firewood to cook. Here begins the new, challenging journey of sourcing or collecting firewood and finding affordable ones to buy.

Figure (3) Illustrate the Firewood Cooking in the Displaced Camp

Source: MEM (2024) Gaza Civil Defence: Hundreds of cases of respiratory diseases recorded, Middle East Monitor, April 20

<https://www.middleeastmonitor.com/20240420-gaza-civil-defence-hundreds-of-cases-of-respiratory-diseases-recorded/>

If you find the firewood, think about the cooking experience using firewood for those accustomed to living in villas. It presents a great difficulty, as heat from the wood might burn their bodies, which happens for some displaced family members. For example, when I take the case of my sister, her face now is burned from the intense heat and the burning of the fire baking and cooking in the extreme heat until she had to go to the hospital and use a lot of medicine to treat the burns in her face. However, the effects of the fire remained on her face due to the severity of the fire, which she still has to face every day as she has to cook and bake on this fire.

It is worth mentioning that the firewood is sold per kilo for about USD\$1-1.5 per kilo, which represents an exorbitant cost for its use that exceeds many times the price of gas at its normal price. This is in addition to the continuous smoke that blinded people and the repeated fires that harmed dozens of tents and their residents as a result of the repeated fires caused by fuel burning in the tents.

4.4.4. Scarce Sourcing of Income and the Lack of Money for the Displaced

In Gaza today, almost all the people are out of work. The unemployment rates in the Gaza Strip before the October 7, 2023 war were about 50% and more than 70% among young people. In light of the war, businesses stopped, industry, agriculture and trade were all destroyed, and tourism disappeared, making the rest of those working lose their jobs. Some government employees or academics received a fraction of their normal salary, representing a quarter or a fifth of their salary at best. To give an example of the best case of this situation, take a university professor who has been getting a salary of about USD\$4,000 and was only receiving half of his salary even before 7th of October, now receiving USD\$220/ month.

Of course, this situation led to the elimination and depletion of the savings of almost all the families in Gaza due to the soaring prices, loss of everything and the long months of the war. Now, almost all people remain without income or any savings and have become more dependent on international aid, besides what could pass through from internal and external solidarity, or whatever could be received from external transfers from relatives in diaspora countries. However, with the liquidity weaknesses in Gaza, even such small transfers from abroad had a soaring commission of 20% and sometimes more than that due to the difficult situation in the strip. All of this contributed to Gaza's great impoverishment and its liquidity depletion.

4.5 Family Charity Lead Initiatives for Feeding, and Distribution of Food Parcels

Because of the severe suffering in life and its requirements, especially concerning cooking and baking, many family initiatives took place as a means for resilience and solidarity. Some of these initiatives got funding from international institutions or generous funding from philanthropists from inside and outside the country. These initiatives, called in Arabic ‘Takea’, were responsible for preparing food daily and distributing it to the displaced in various ways. The foods distributed vary in quantity, quality, with or without the availability of meat, depending on the amount of funding. In general, shelters have been a good phenomenon, relieving people of many of the necessities of life in tents in light of the lack of work and salary and people running out of money.

For example, in the first author's family ‘Takea’ food is prepared per day for about 400 families, with an average of 5 members per family and an average of 5-10 dollars per family meal, depending on food awareness and the availability of meat. The cooperation was local, Arab and international through individuals, charities and international institutions such as WCK and the UNRWA Foundation. Which cooperated with these ‘Takea’s’ in providing both labor and extra cooking requirements, provided that ‘Takea’ ensure consistency in feeding the nearby displaced families.

On the other hand, the ‘Takea’, through generous funding from family philanthropists located in the Gulf countries, the' distributed thousands of food parcels to displaced residents of tents, which contributed to providing some of their needs and reducing financial costs for many of these displaced people. The ‘Takea’ also contributed to providing many tents and covers for shelters for many of the displaced people who cannot find shelter or have the tools to prepare any type of shelter.

Figure (4) Photo showing the First Author's family visit to one of the displacement camps where they gathered under the Tree between the camp tents.

Courtesy: 1st Author

4.6. The Displaced Multipurpose Tent

Around any displacement camp, you will find a small shade that is built between the tents to be used as a multipurpose place. It would be the family prayer area and the displacement camp general room, where the Qur'an memory group holds their gathering and where several children's memorisation classes are held. There are about 5 sessions per day, including 40-50 children.

Figure (5) Photo showing the multi-purpose tent in the large families camps

Courtesy: 1st Author

This picture gives an example of what some families managed to do to maintain their minimum cultural gatherings. It is like a multipurpose tent that the displaced use for prayers and Qur'an memorisation classes in the family camp.

4.7. Specialisation and Division of Labor among Displaced

Specialisation, organisation, and setting working hours for family members in the tent have become important and routine issues. Everyone is accountable, there are those who bear the responsibility of providing water and stand for hours in line for water from wells and distributors. Some bear the responsibility of selling surplus goods to provide shekels to buy some of the family's needs. Others have the task of ensuring the battery, lighting, mobile phones, etc are charged. While the mothers and daughters are responsible for cooking and washing, the men collect Firewood and often a fire for cooking. This is a daily routine and a survival task regardless of who you are.

4.8. Impact of Aid Theft

Despite the great importance and urgent need for aid, Israel's insistence on spreading security chaos and deliberately bombing any police or security agency working to control the regime has led to the spread of gangs stealing much of the aid across the borders. Many of what enters through the Rafah crossing for UNRWA and other international institutions have been stolen.

For example, if 60 trucks loaded with aid manage to enter the Rafah Border, at least 30 trucks would be completely stolen. One could also notice that these gangs steal trucks loaded with expensive materials and leave the cheap ones. The first author confirm that he witnessed that once 20 trucks entered the Rafah border and were completely stolen.

As for stolen goods, they go to the market directly at market price after those who deserve them are deprived of obtaining them for free, negatively affecting the home front and weakening confidence in the Gaza's ruling system. We have appealed and tried a lot and are still seeking solutions to prevent the theft of aid, but to no avail.

4.9. Problems and Choices

Because of overcrowding and the intersection of housing with poverty, destitution, and the urgent need for everything, and because of weak morals, many problems, divorces, and armed attacks have spread, which we consider to be a result of the security chaos that needs to be controlled. This is despite all the efforts that the area leaders (called 'Mukhtars') have managed to solve complex problems through mediation between conflicting families. 'Mukhtars' played an important role in this field, many risks were eliminated or mitigated through their grateful efforts, besides their dedication of time, and money (where possible). These efforts are especially appreciated in a time when movement around is life-threatening and where the costs for movement and transportation are considered to sacrifice other life essentials.

Some large extended families prepared a family council to build or maintain cohesion of the family members with the challenges of the displacement. The family council focused on managing the family's internal affairs and solving their problems. It also became the source for communicating with other families regarding survival and resilience decisions. In the Al-Miqdad family, for example, the 'Takea' played this role, as it was a point where the family gathering was easy. This helped to overcome any family challenges and strengthened the family relationships.

4.10. The Phenomenon of Marriage in Tents

According to our knowledge and follow-up, we have discovered that most of those who were engaged before the war decided to get married. This was encouraged by the almost absence of costs, as what is required is to provide a tent for the newlyweds, and in such cases, institutions sympathise and provide them with a tent. The wedding here does not require lunch or other costs, which encourages young people to get married.

The limitations of the displacement did not stop at those engaged before the war, but we found many cases of new marriages during the war, especially with young women whose husbands were martyred in the war.

4.11. Transportation During Living Displacement

During this aggression on Gaza, tens of thousands of cars and trucks were bombed, which made people cautious of using vehicles. With cars not being allowed to enter the Gaza Strip, the problem worsened further, resulting in a return to the use of old, worn-out cars, which have major negative effects on human health. With the lack of availability of gasoline (\$40 per litre) and diesel fuel (\$30 per litre), people started to use frying oil instead of diesel fuel for their essential distances. This has exacerbated the environmental pollution issue in Gaza and created a further negative impact on human health. Meanwhile, the prices of transferring people during displacement soured and increased tenfold. Even the costs of transporting luggage have increased tenfold whether using cars or others means.

The other challenge is the destroyed roads that make travelling by car challenging. For example, suppose a displaced family wants to shift from 'Khan Yunis' to 'Al-Zawaida' which is only 12 kilometers in a normal situation. In that case, the fare is 3-4 shekels, and the duration is only 15 minutes. Now, with the total destruction of Gaza roads, we need 3 transportation costs 20 shekels and a duration of more than two hours.

As for means of transportation, it has become of different types, including the traditional 4-seater car, but it now carries 12 passengers. This car was developed by adding a towed cart to transport passengers. Cargo carts were also used to transport passengers. The most common means, especially for short distances, were carts drawn by horses and donkeys.

4.12. The Difficulty of Visiting Relatives or Friends

Speaking of transportation and movement, the first author mentions that he visited the displacement camp where my brothers and sisters were only 10 kilometres away from our camp, and it took him more than two hours. This journey was partly done for part of it on foot, then on a horse-drawn carriage, a third in a freight, and a fourth in a car. Then, the journey was concluded by walking on foot until he arrived at his relatives' camp. After arriving, the first author sat with his sister in the tent and heard the sounds of explosions above them. We quickly left the tent to find the wing of a suicide drone that had fallen right next to the tent, four meters away. The plane continued to explode with its missile 200 meters away, but luckily, he and his sister survived.

Figure (6) A Piece from the Drone where the metal is 120 cm long and 10 cm wide. It shows the shape of a sharp sword that, if it hits anyone, could cut them into pieces.

Courtesy: 1st Author

4.13. Resilience is not a Choice for the Displaced

The reality of the displacement represents the extreme difficulty and despair of life in the midst of heat, unavailability of life-essential food or clean/drinking water, war, noise, environmental pollution, hazards, scattered families, daily deaths of some of the relatives or friends and insecurity for all the time.

During this extremely harsh reality, hardiness and resilience are not choices. On the other hand, one finds some people are astonishing with persistence, perseverance, and tolerance while also normal to see others who became, due to high stress, incapable of any endurance. In this situation, you have to turn only to God. We do not find among them anything but that we are not saturated with the remembrance that's well of God, and they have total acceptance of that and that it is a test of their resilience. Yet you find misery and distress in people's faces before they are displaced again, during displacement and after being settled, as all Gazans never experienced such aggression or such disappointment with their Arab leaders, and powerless international community.

Being displaced, is a place and a status where you can't distinguish between the rich and the poor, as everyone became poor and everyone lost what they had, and whoever had a surplus of money it ran out during ten months of war and unemployment with the extremely high prices of everything that is available. The dominant characteristic of the displaced people who have uncomplete tents is agility, but also weight loss, the majority lost a weight of between 10-30 kilograms due to the lack of sufficient food. Therefore, malnutrition and hunger are common, in addition to the hard effort in transporting water, collecting firewood, lighting a fire, and thinking about the outcomes and the uncertain future.

It can be said here that the people in Gaza are in dire need of an end to the war, as they are suffering from killing and displacement and cannot participate in combat operations. The Israeli army does not avoid risks, but rather deliberately targets civilians under the pretext that these people's resilience is what protects the resistance. Almost all the displaced people keep sending signals to the Hamas and Palestinian negotiators about the importance of reaching an honourable agreement after these great sacrifices.

5.0. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

The displacement diaries from Gaza during the 2023/2024 war provide a vital lens through which the harsh realities of conflict are documented and understood. These narratives reveal the immense challenges displaced families face, from the dangers of movement and the struggle to find safe shelter, to the daily hardships of living without basic necessities like water, gas, and food. Despite the adversity, the resilience of the Gazan people shines through as they adapt to their circumstances through community-driven initiatives, specialization within displacement camps, and unwavering solidarity. However, this resilience is not merely a choice but a necessity for survival in an environment where resources are scarce and external support is limited.

The insights gathered from these diaries underscore the urgent need for sustained international attention, advocacy, and humanitarian aid to address the ongoing crisis in Gaza. Through continued documentation and support, there is hope that the voices of the displaced will contribute to lasting change and a future where such suffering is no longer a daily reality. Also, the insights gained from these personal accounts can inform future peacebuilding and reconciliation efforts. Understanding the lived experiences of those affected by the conflict is crucial for developing policies that address the root causes of displacement and support sustainable peace.

In summary, displacement diaries from Gaza during the 2023/2024 war are vital for documenting personal experiences, humanising the conflict, countering misinformation, raising awareness, providing psychological relief, preserving culture, and informing future peacebuilding efforts.

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